

Design and Analysis of a Morphing Trailing Edge Structure

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1 Abstract

The need for a next generation of air vehicles that has high performance and low environmental impact has gained during the past years due to the "green-liner" demands on civil aeronautics¹.

Morphing airframe technologies represent a very promising area of investigation in the field of aircraft design. The use of morphing structures on the new generation wings will enhance the flight performance and at the same time will significantly reduce the power consumption, the noise emission and the overall aircraft environmental impact^{2,3,4}.

Several morphing concepts have been proposed for the conventional high lift devices^{5,6,7}. Most of them have developed some sophistic morphing mechanisms and achieved effective results. However, these design methods of morphing wing are impeded when they are used in the engineering practice for the following facts.

1. The morphing trailing edge needs enormous power to morph to the desired shape.
2. Some morphing trailing edge schemes have intricate and cumbersome mechanisms which seriously reduce the reliability and increase the weight of these systems.
3. Due to the limited driving range the common smart actuators is difficult to meet the need of large deformation.
4. The location and the form of the actuator significantly influence the last shape of the

morphing structures. However, most of the developed design methods leave these factors out of consideration.

In this paper, compliant structures optimization design approach based on parametric analysis for a small unmanned aerial vehicle(UAV) is proposed which has overcome the above drawbacks to a great extent.

Compliant structures optimization design approach based parametric analysis divides the optimization process into two stages. Firstly, the topology optimization was conducted to determine the optimal topology of the compliant trailing edge structure which consider the actuation location, the actuation form and the actuation size. An parametric analysis approach based on the essential topology optimization was developed to obtain the optimal topology and determine the actuator condition correspondingly. To compare the deformed and target curves, the two curves was first expressed in terms of two sets of sampling points that are evenly distributed along the curve lengths, as shown in Fig. 1. The least square error (LSE) deviation is defined as the sum of Euclidian distance between each pair of sampling points on the two curves. This is shown in Eq.(1), where n is the total number of sampling points; $(u_{def,i})$ and $(u_{tar,i})$ are the displacement of the sampling points along the deformed and target curves respectively.

$$LSE = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i (u_{def,i} - u_{tar,i})^2 \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

The airfoil achieves the optimum aerodynamic performs as LSE is close to zero, therefore, the object function of the topology optimization problem is LSE in this work. Fig. 2 shows the model of the topology optimization problem. A Optistruct topology optimization procedure with re-development method by Hypermath was implemented. Fig. 3 shows the density contour of the optimal topology. In addition, the corresponding optimal actuator condition is -5mm x-direction displacement with h=0.5.

Subsequently, the detail size optimization was implemented in order to achieve the desired deflected shape. Fig. 4 shows the model of the size optimization. The result of the deformed shape and the optimal height of all beam section are illustrated in Fig. 5 and table 1. This shows that the final shape of the compliant trailing edge is coincide with the target shape almost.

Fig. 1 Target curve, target curve and final curve

Fig. 2 The model of the topology optimization

Fig. 3 The density of material contour

Fig. 4 The model of the size optimization

Fig. 5 The contrast of the target curve and the final curve

Table 1 The optimal height of all beam sections

PROP- TYPE	PROP- ID	ITEM- CODE	PROP- VALUE(mm)
PBAR	1	DIM2	2.00E+00
PBAR	2	DIM2	1.00E+00
PBAR	3	DIM2	1.00E+00
PBAR	4	DIM2	1.00E+00
PBAR	5	DIM2	1.00E+00
PBAR	6	DIM2	2.00E+00
PBAR	7	DIM2	2.00E+00
PBAR	8	DIM2	2.00E+00
PBAR	9	DIM2	2.00E+00
PBAR	10	DIM2	2.00E+00
PBAR	11	DIM2	2.00E+00

Thirdly, a nonlinear finite element analysis was conducted in order to examine the maximum stress. As the result of the Abaqus shows that the maximum Von

Mises stress is 50.87MPa below the ABS yield strength 71.8MPa. Furthermore, the final deformed shape and the target shape of the compliant trailing edge is match very well.

Fig. 6 Compliant trailing edge stress

Fig. 7 The deformed curve and the target curve

Finally, in parallel with the trailing edge design study, a prototype physical model, the actuator and the test-bed were constructed to validate morphing capacity of the intended shape change. Fig. 8 shows photographs of the physical model of the morphing compliant trailing edge structure.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 8 morphing trailing edge physical model shown in 0 degrees (fig. a) and +20degrees (fig. b) positions

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